

SIMULATION OF THE THERMO-STAMPING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The thermo-stamping process involves forming a part with a pre-consolidated plate of thermoplastic composite previously heated in an infra-red oven and cooling down at the contact of the mould. This process seems to be a promising way for the mass production of composite parts. However this process is complex to simulate due to the multi-physics background (textile deformation, thermal shock, rubbing,...) and “trial and error” tests campaigns can be expensive. This study focuses on the measurement and characterization of the process parameters and the material's behaviour, to simulate the forming phase of the composite sheet and obtain a part without defects. This phase is often considered as a major source of failures (wrinkles, lack of matrix,...). The mechanical characterisation of the shear and bending behaviour of the plate in temperature enables the numerical simulation of the forming process. The experiment makes it possible to determine the consolidation time necessary in order to optimize the fabrication time as a function of the material used and of its thickness. This measurements and simulations optimize the production of this fast process but tricky to tune.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the last years, the place of composite materials in the industry has significantly increased, especially those with a thermoplastic matrix. However, a major drawback of composites materials is the processing time, especially for the mass production. The thermo-stamping process involves forming a composites part from a pre-consolidated thermoplastic composite plate and can be decomposed in two steps. First, the pre-consolidated sheet is rapidly heated above the melting point via an infra-red source. Secondly, the heated pre-consolidated sheet is transferred to a press-punch and undergoes a forming stage. During the forming stage, the pre-consolidated sheet starts to cool down quickly as soon as contact is made with the punch and the mould.

This process seems to be a promising way to reduce processing time and to produce a part per minute (depending on the matrix, the thickness and the infra-red lamp). However the fast variations of form and temperature during the second step imply difficulties to tune the process parameters and obtain a piece without defaults. To limit the expensive “trial and error” tests campaigns at the part scale, a simulation of the forming supplied by the result of the mechanical characterization in shear and bending tests of the input material seems essential. Moreover the parameters are interdependent [1] (temperature, speed, time)

2 PRE-CONSOLIDATED PLATE

The materials used are pre-consolidated sheets of woven fabric with a thermoplastic matrix (see Figure 1). Unlike the powdered or the comingled woven fabric, in the pre-consolidated sheet, the

fabric and the different layers are already impregnated by the matrix and don't need to be impregnated during the thermo-stamping process.

Indeed the consolidation phase of the thermo-stamping process is too short to allow the matrix to flow around the fibre, especially around the fibrils. Therefore, the used of powdered or the comingled woven fabric is not suitable. Furthermore, in such materials, as the different layers are not in contact, the space in between creates insulation zones avoiding the conduction of heat through the thickness via the infra-red source.

Figure 1: Example of pre-consolidated plates

3 MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR

A macroscopic approach is used, considering a Representative Elementary Cell of the woven fabric (R.E.C.). A R.E.C. is the most little element of the woven fabric which can represent all the woven fabric by only translations (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Representative Elementary Cell of a woven (Twill2/2)

The “red” R.E.C. will be preferred [2] to simulate the forming of the composites: the side must be on the centre of the yarn and not in the void. A semi-discrete approach developed by N. Hamila [3, 4] representing this R.E.C. by membrane elements and considering 3 kinds of loading by the warp and weft tensions, in-plane shear and bending moments (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Loading on a R.E.C.: (a) tensions; (b) in-plane shear moment; (c) bending moment

In the R.E.C., the direction 1 is defined by the warp direction, direction 2 by the weft direction and the direction 3 is the direction perpendicular to 1 and 2.

The calculation of the strain is based on the calculation of the virtual work theorem:

$$W_{\text{ext}}(\bar{\eta}) - W_{\text{int}}(\bar{\eta}) = W_{\text{acc}}(\bar{\eta}) \quad (1)$$

Where $W_{\text{ext}}(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual external work contributions, $W_{\text{int}}(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual internal work contributions, $W_{\text{acc}}(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual acceleration work contributions, for any displacement field $\bar{\eta}$ equal to zero on the boundary.

With:

$$W_{\text{int}}(\bar{\eta}) = W_{\text{int}}^t(\bar{\eta}) + W_{\text{int}}^s(\bar{\eta}) + W_{\text{int}}^b(\bar{\eta}) \quad (2)$$

Where $W_{\text{int}}^t(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual internal tensile work contributions, $W_{\text{int}}^s(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual internal in plane shear moment work contributions and $W_{\text{int}}^b(\bar{\eta})$ is the virtual internal bending moments work contributions.

3.1 Tensile modulus

During the tensile test of a woven fabric in the warp or the weft direction, two strain phases occur [5]. Firstly, the crimp phase, with a low modulus and secondly, the yarn elongation phase with a much higher modulus (around 70GPa for the fibre glass and 200GPa for the carbon fibre). The tensile work

W_{int}^t is:

$$W_{\text{int}}^t(\bar{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{REC}}} \left(\varepsilon_{11}(\bar{\eta}) \cdot T^{11}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}) \cdot L_1^p + \varepsilon_{22}(\bar{\eta}) \cdot T^{22}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}) \cdot L_2^p \right) \quad (3)$$

Where $\varepsilon_{11}(\bar{\eta})$ and $\varepsilon_{22}(\bar{\eta})$ are respectively the virtual strain in the direction of the warp and the weft, L_1^p and L_2^p the length of the R.E.C. respectively in the warp and the weft direction. The tension $T^{11}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22})$ and $T^{22}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22})$ depending of the strain are following the warp and weft direction.

3.2 Shear moment

The in-plane shear moment $M^s(\gamma_{12})$ is the principal parameter that characterises the drability [6] depending on $\gamma_{12}(\bar{\eta})$, the angle under the warp and weft with:

$$W_{\text{int}}^s(\bar{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{REC}}} \gamma_{12}(\bar{\eta}) \cdot M^s(\gamma_{12}) \quad (4)$$

The wrinkles usually appear near the zone under shear [7].

3.3 Bending moment

The bending moment $M^b(\chi)$ gives the form of the wrinkles depending of $\chi_{13}(\bar{\eta})$, the curvature in the 13 plane and $\chi_{23}(\bar{\eta})$ the curvature in the plane 23 with:

$$W_{\text{int}}^b(\bar{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{REC}}} \left((\chi_{13})(\bar{\eta}) \cdot M^b(\chi_{13}) + (\chi_{23})(\bar{\eta}) \cdot M^b(\chi_{23}) \right) \quad (5)$$

4 CHARACTERISATION

The characterisation of the pre-consolidated plate is really specific as it requires to be conducted under the same temperature conditions as the process.

4.1 Tensile modulus

A tensile test with a load of 1N/yarn was conducted on pre-consolidated plates at various temperatures (under the melting point and at the process temperatures). The load of 1N/yarn corresponds to the maximal charge of a yarn during the bending test or the bias-extension describe in the next paragraphs. The different specimens didn't show a significant extension under the tensile load at the different temperatures (see Figure 4). Considering this observations, the crimp phase was neglected in the simulations.

Figure 4: Pre-consolidated plate at 68°C and 220°C

4.2 Shear moment

The shear moment was measured using the bias-extension test.

Figure 5: Bias-extension test

During the bias-extension test, the load applied at the jaw, $F(u)$ and its displacement u are measured (see Figure 5). It is assumed that during the bias-extension test there is no translation sliding between the warp and the weft yarns. This hypothesis can't be used with an angle upper than the maximum shear angle, that's why an angle maximum of 40° will be used in this experiment. The yarns are considered inextensible. This hypothesis can be used in this case due to the high Young's modulus of the fibre and the load applied on the specimen (less than 20 Newtons). In this conditions the shear angle γ_{12} is calculated with:

$$\gamma_{12} = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \cdot \arccos\left(\frac{D+u}{\sqrt{2} \cdot D}\right) \quad (6)$$

The power applied by the testing machine is supposed to be transmitted by a shear mechanism into the sample, therefore:

$$F(u) \cdot \dot{u} \cdot S_u = M^s(\gamma_{12}) \cdot S_c \cdot \dot{\gamma}_{12} + M^s\left(\frac{\gamma_{12}}{2}\right) \cdot S_b \cdot \frac{\dot{\gamma}_{12}}{2} \quad (7)$$

This gives the in-plane shear moment $M^s(\gamma_{12})$ as a function of $M^s\left(\frac{\gamma_{12}}{2}\right)$, the shear moment in the half shear zone:

$$M^s(\gamma_{12}) = F(u) \cdot \frac{S_u \cdot \dot{u}}{S_c \cdot \dot{\gamma}_{12}} + M^s\left(\frac{\gamma_{12}}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{S_b}{2 \cdot S_c} \quad (8)$$

The experiment confirms [8] that the shear moment highly depends on the temperature (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Example of influence of the temperature on the shearing moment

4.3 Bending moment

The bending moment is measured by the Cantilever test in temperature by the method developed by Biao Liang [9]. Thermocouples were placed on an other identical sample behind the one on which the deformed shape was measured, in order not to disturb the measurement (see Figure 7). The deformed shape was captured with an image analysis software.

Figure 7: Example of a Cantilever test in temperature

The deformed shape enable to obtain the moment as a function of the curvature.

5 MEASUREMENT OF THE TEMPERATURES

Pre-consolidated plates were instrumented with thermocouples on the surface of a blank and in the centre (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Place of the thermocouples in an instrumented plate with a thickness of 2 mm

The instrumented plate is stamped and the temperature is recorded. Unlike to the thermo-forming process [10], this experiment shows a thermal shock at the surface of the plate (see Figure 9) and the necessity to form the part while the surface temperature is still above the melting point. This test highlights the consolidation time necessary before the part is ejected in order to optimize the processing time. The non-compliance of these time will lead to defaults, like lack of matrix, form defaults, voids [11] to name few.

Figure 9: Example with a plate of glass/PP stamped

6 SIMULATION

The moduli obtained by the experimental characterisation above are implemented in PlasFib (calculation code developed by the INSA of Lyon) to simulate the forming stage. Figure 10 shows a comparison of the formed geometry.

Figure 10: Comparison between simulation and experiment

The simulation (see Figure 11) predicts the position of the yarns to design the thickness of the product and its feasibility.

Figure 11: Example of simulation

However other factors occurring during the processing are difficult to take into consideration in the simulations. These factors may influence the form of the fabric outside of the mould.

7 CONCLUSION

The thermo-stamping process seems to be a promising way for the mass production. However this process is difficult to tune and requires a knowledge of the materials used. Moreover the parameters are interdependent (temperature, speed, time) which adds complexity to the investigation of the best parameters to optimize the production of a part with a good material health. To produce parts with a complex form, simulations can avoid doing an expensive “trial and error” approach which saves time and investment. The simulation has limits, indeed other factors in the process environment are difficult to simulate and influence the form of the textile outside of the mould. However, in order to design the final part in static and crash, the orientation fibre seems essential and is given by the forming simulation.

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